

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF LEARNING MANY LANGUAGES AS A YOUNG CHILD

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ABSTRACT

This article informs the important aspects of learning a lot of languages to young learners, as well as, the positive impacts to people who speak more than one language have improved memory, problem-solving and critical-thinking skill, enhanced concentration, ability to multitask and better listening skills.

INTRODUCTION

A great deal of scientists mentioned that it is important to learn a second language at an early age, there are several reasons that respond the question, "Why educate many languages to young learners?" For example, creating a positive and fun learning environment can supply youngsters with a powerful foundation for triumph in more advanced lessons later in their academic careers. Bilingual kids acquire faster and without difficulties, have enhanced problem solving ability and creativeness, and have more profession opportunities in adult ages. They also notice that it easier to link with other cultures which makes them more open-minded and lenient of variety, and they are less probable to experience age-related mental disease as they reach old age. The most importantly, it is much easier to learn a second language at a very young age.

In addition, educating the second language is not as heavy as it used to be. Scientists are continually studying second language acquisition and improving new methodologies to help children educate faster. And the increasing request of language programs have created a whole new market of international holiday camps with language courses where young learners can enjoy their lovely activities and learn a new language at the same period. One of the great advantages of learning the second language at a young age is that kids learn languages faster and easier. They have much time to study, less to learn, fewer prohibitions, and a brain designed for language learning. In brief, educating your kid the second language from childhood rescues them from having to learn a second language as an adult age. On a biological level, young learners are like sponges.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The brain of a kid is created to absorb new information unintentionally. They do this similarly to the way that we, as adults, unwittingly learn songs' lyrics, rhythms, and melodies. Dr. Paul Thompson, a neurology professor at UCLA, and his team argued that the brain systems particularized in acquiring new languages raise sharply from about six years old till pubescence. Then these systems primarily shut down and stop increasing between 11 and 15,

during pubescence. Between the age of 10 and 12, babies can distinguish between all sounds through all languages. Hereafter, according to their exposure to languages, they are able to only distinguish between the language sounds which are essential to create meaning. The Japanese language does not differentiate between the “L” and the “R” sounds. Japanese kids before 10 months old, able to hear the varieties between these sounds. Then, between 10 and 12 months old, they lose their ability to distinguish. Another one of the advantages of learning the second language at a very young age is that young learners think more simply than adults. They consume less words, easy sentence structures, and think less conceptionally.

Youngsters who are acquiring the second language are not overpowered by the activity of communicating their concrete conceptions and feelings in their second language. Then, as these kids progress into adults, they learn to express themselves in both their mother and second languages. However, adults face the challenging task of translating complicated sentence structures and abstract apprehension to be able to entirely depict themselves in their second languages. Can you imagine about the books you read in the childhood compared to the books you read nowadays? Reminisce it took many years of studying and required reading to be able to comprehend the texts you are able to read now. The similar applies to writing, listening, and even speaking. To be able to communicate as you do in your mother tongue, it took at least 15 years of formal education.

One of the biggest advantages of learning a second language early on is time. Time is on the learners' side. They have the ability to begin small and ordinary and progress to both advanced mental and communication levels at the same time. Kids have a great benefit over adults as second language learners. Young generation who learn the second language become adult to be expert creative thinkers and problem-solvers. The brains of children experience a permanent workout from childhood as they try to clarify which language to speak and when. Additionally, scientists have noticed that bilingual and enhanced problem-solving skilled children are better at planning, multi-tasking and concentrating as well as they score higher on standardized tests. By educating your children the second language at a young age, you may direct them to success.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bilingual children are permanently experiencing a mental training as they clarify through more than one language method to communicate. Researchers and teachers discouraged second language learning in the 20th century. The second language was thought to intervene with kids' cognitive and intellectual development. However, there is facts that interference of language systems is experienced by bilingual children, it results that the internal controversy that bilingual kids experience prepares them to be skillful problem solvers. Collective facts from several studies illustrates that learning the second language enhance the brain's executive function. This means that bilingual kids are better at:

Problem solving

Planning

Concentration

Multitasking

Increased exam scores are one of the many advantages of learning a second language at a young age. Learning a second language helps students do better on standardized tests like the

SAT verbal part and the American College Test (ACT). The reality that a student's test results improve the more time they spend studying a second language. Another benefit of acquiring a second language at a young age is the motivation to be creative. Numerous studies have supported it. Language developing is thought to progress by usual processes of learning in which children get the forms, meanings, and consume of words and expressions from the linguistic input. Youngsters often begin reproducing the words that they are repetitive exposed to. The system in which we improve language skills is general, however, the main discussion is how the rules of syntax are acquired. There are theories of syntactic development separated two major groups: an empiricist account by which kids learn all of the syntactic rules from the linguistic input, and a nativist approach by which other principles of syntax are inborn and are transferred through the humans' genomes.

The nativist theory, suggested by Noam Chomsky, mentioned that language is an unusual human performance, and able to be attributed to either " the millions of years of evolution" or " the principles of neural organization that might be even more profoundly grounded in physical law". Chomsky argued [5.25] that a lot off kids have an innate language acquiring device (LAD). In theory, the LAD is a space of the brain which has a set of universal syntactic rules for whole languages. This device supports learners with the quality to make sense of knowledge and build novel sentences with minimum external input and little experience. Chomsky's mentioned that is consist upon the opinion that what youngsters hear—their linguistic input—is scanty to interpret how they come to learn language. He notes that linguistic input from the environment is limited and full of mistakes. That is why, it is impossible for kids to learn linguistic information merely from their environment this view assumed by nativists. On the other hand, children acquire this LAD, the fact that, they can learn language in spite of incompleteness of information from their environment. Their scale to acquire language is also attributed to the theory of common grammar (UG), that posits the certain set of structural rules are inborn to people, autonomous of sensory adventure. This sign has controlled linguistic theory for more than fifty years and maintained highly influential, as evidenced by the pile of articles in books and journals. The empiricist theory suggests, contra Chomsky, that there is adequate information in the linguistic input kids acquire that is why, there is no require to assume an inborn language acquisition device exists. Rather than the LAD brings out specifically for language, empiricists consider that general brain progresses are competent for language acquisition. While this process, it is essential for the kid to actively engross with their environment.

CONCLUSION

For the children to learn language, the parents or caregivers adopts a specific way of properly communicating with the children; this is familiar as child-directed speech (CDS). CDS is consumed so that children can get the important linguistic information needed for their language. Empiricism is a common method and occasionally goes along with the interactionist approach. The statistical language acquisition, that falls down under empiricist theory, suggests that babies acquire language by means of example concept.

The tests are called the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking (TTCT) are one of the most used creativity tests created by Ellis Paul Torrance in 1962. These tests are created to admeasure

“divergent thinking” or thinking outside the norm, thinking creatively. They identify participants’ divergent thinking in four areas: flexibility, fluency, elaboration, and originality.

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